

CLASSICAL AND $\mathbb{C}$ -MOTIVIC ADAMS CHARTS

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ABSTRACT. This document contains large-format Adams charts that compute 2-complete stable homotopy groups, both in the classical context and in the $\mathbb{C}$ -motivic context. The charts are essentially complete through the 90-stem and contain partial results to the 110-stem.

This document contains large-format Adams charts that compute 2-complete stable homotopy groups, both in the classical context and in the $\mathbb{C}$ -motivic context. The charts are essentially complete through the 90-stem and contain partial results to the 110-stem.

The charts are intended to be viewed electronically. The authors can supply versions that are suitable for printing.

Justifications for these computations appear in [3], [4], [5], [7], [9], [10], [12], [17], [18], and [19]. Older references that justify many of the classical computations include [1], [2], [6], [13], [14], [15], and [16].

This document supersedes [8], which included Adams charts for the cofiber of τ . The charts associated to the cofiber of τ now appear in the separate manuscript [11].

1. THE E_2 -PAGE OF THE CLASSICAL ADAMS SPECTRAL SEQUENCE

This chart shows the classical Adams spectral sequence. The chart is complete to the 90-stem, with partial results through the 110-stem.

- (1) Gray dots indicate copies of $\mathbb{F}_2$.
- (2) Vertical lines indicate h_0 multiplications.
- (3) Lines of slope 1 indicate h_1 multiplications.
- (4) Lines of slope $1/3$ indicate h_2 multiplications.
- (5) Light blue lines of slope -2 indicate Adams d_2 differentials.
- (6) Red lines of slope -3 indicate Adams d_3 differentials.
- (7) Green lines of slope -4 indicate Adams d_4 differentials.
- (8) Blue lines of slope -5 indicate Adams d_5 differentials.
- (9) Orange lines of slope less than -5 indicate higher Adams differentials.
- (10) Dashed lines indicate possible Adams differentials. Beyond the 90-stem, possible Adams differentials are not indicated.

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2. THE E_3 -PAGE OF THE CLASSICAL ADAMS SPECTRAL SEQUENCE

This chart shows the E_3 -page of the classical Adams spectral sequence. The chart is complete to the 90-stem, with partial results through the 110-stem. See Section 1 for instructions on interpreting the chart. Beyond the 90-stem, possible Adams differentials are not indicated.

3. THE E_∞ -PAGE OF THE CLASSICAL ADAMS SPECTRAL SEQUENCE

This chart indicates the E_∞ -page of the classical Adams spectral sequence. The chart is complete to the 90-stem, with partial results through the 95-stem. Beyond the 90-stem, possible Adams differentials are not indicated. Beyond the 70-stem, not all hidden extensions have been resolved; see [10] for more details.

See Section 1 for instructions on interpreting the chart. In addition:

- (1) Red lines indicate hidden 2 extensions.
- (2) Blue lines indicate hidden η extensions.
- (3) Green lines indicate hidden ν extensions.

4. THE E_2 -PAGE OF THE MOTIVIC ADAMS SPECTRAL SEQUENCE

This chart indicates the cohomology of the Steenrod algebra, i.e., the $\mathbb{C}$ -motivic Adams E_2 -page, as well as the Adams d_2 differentials, through the 110-stem. For legibility, the chart is divided into two pages with different scales.

- (1) Gray dots indicate copies of $\mathbb{M}_2$.
- (2) Red dots indicate copies of $\mathbb{M}_2/\tau$.
- (3) Blue dots indicate copies of $\mathbb{M}_2/\tau^2$.
- (4) Green dots indicate copies of $\mathbb{M}_2/\tau^3$.
- (5) Purple dots indicate copies of $\mathbb{M}_2/\tau^k$ for some $k \geq 4$.
- (6) Vertical lines indicate h_0 multiplications. For legibility, the colors of these lines matches the colors of their targets.
- (7) Lines of slope 1 indicate h_1 multiplications. For legibility, the colors of these lines matches the colors of their targets.
- (8) Lines of slope 1/3 indicate h_2 multiplications. For legibility, the colors of these lines matches the colors of their targets.
- (9) Red arrows indicate infinite towers of h_1 multiplications, all of which are annihilated by τ .
- (10) Magenta lines indicate that an extension hits τ times a generator. For example, $h_0 \cdot h_0 h_2 = \tau h_1^3$ in the 3-stem.
- (11) Orange lines indicate that an extension hits τ^k times a generator, for some $k \geq 2$. For example, $h_0 \cdot h_0^3 x = \tau^2 h_0 e_0 g$ in the 37-stem.
- (12) Blue lines of slope -2 indicate Adams d_2 differentials.
- (13) Magenta lines of slope -2 indicate that an Adams d_2 differential hits τ times a generator. For example, $d_2(h_0 c_2) = \tau h_1^2 e_1$ in the 40-stem.
- (14) Orange lines of slope -2 indicate that an Adams d_2 differential hits τ^k times a generator for some $k \geq 2$. For example, $d_2(h_0 y) = \tau^2 h_0 e_0 g$ in the 37-stem.

The use of color is well-illustrated by the element $h_2 g^2$ in the 43-stem. The dot is green, indicating that $\tau^3 h_2 g^2$ is zero. The outgoing blue lines indicate that $h_0 \cdot h_2 g^2$ and $h_2 \cdot h_2 g^2$ are annihilated by τ^2 . The incoming magenta line indicates

that $h_2 \cdot \tau g^2$ equals $\tau h_2 g^2$, and the incoming orange line indicates that $h_1 \cdot Ph_1^3 h_5$ equals $\tau^2 h_2 g^2$.

5. THE E_3 -PAGE OF THE MOTIVIC ADAMS SPECTRAL SEQUENCE

This chart indicates the Adams d_3 differentials on the E_3 -page of the motivic Adams spectral sequence through the 110-stem. The chart is complete through the 95-stem. Beyond the 95-stem, possible differentials are not indicated.

See Section 4 for instructions on interpreting the chart. In addition:

- (1) Blue lines of slope -3 indicate Adams d_3 differentials.
- (2) Magenta lines of slope -3 indicate that an Adams d_3 differential hits τ times a generator.
- (3) Orange lines of slope -3 indicate that an Adams d_3 differential hits τ^k times a generator for some $k \geq 2$.

6. THE E_4 -PAGE OF THE MOTIVIC ADAMS SPECTRAL SEQUENCE

This chart indicates the Adams d_4 differentials on the E_4 -page of the motivic Adams spectral sequence through the 110-stem. The chart is complete through the 95-stem. Beyond the 95-stem, possible differentials are not indicated.

See Section 4 for instructions on interpreting the chart. In addition:

- (1) Blue lines of slope -4 indicate Adams d_4 differentials.
- (2) Magenta lines of negative slope indicate that an Adams differential hits τ times a generator.
- (3) Orange lines of negative slope indicate that an Adams differential hits τ^k times a generator for some $k \geq 2$.

7. THE E_5 -PAGE OF THE MOTIVIC ADAMS SPECTRAL SEQUENCE

This chart indicates the Adams d_5 differentials on the E_5 -page of the motivic Adams spectral sequence. The chart is complete through the 95-stem.

See Section 4 for instructions on interpreting the chart. In addition:

- (1) Blue lines of slope -5 indicate Adams d_5 differentials.
- (2) Magenta lines of negative slope indicate that an Adams differential hits τ times a generator.
- (3) Orange lines of negative slope indicate that an Adams differential hits τ^k times a generator for some $k \geq 2$.

8. THE E_6 -PAGE OF THE MOTIVIC ADAMS SPECTRAL SEQUENCE

This chart indicates the higher Adams differentials on the E_6 -page of the motivic Adams spectral sequence. The chart is complete to the 90-stem, with partial results through the 95-stem.

See Section 4 for instructions on interpreting the chart. In addition:

- (1) Blue lines of negative slope indicate Adams d_r differentials for some $r \geq 6$.
- (2) Magenta lines of negative slope indicate that an Adams differential hits τ times a generator.
- (3) Orange lines of negative slope indicate that an Adams differential hits τ^k times a generator for some $k \geq 2$.
- (4) Dashed lines indicate possible Adams differentials.

9. THE E_∞ -PAGE OF THE MOTIVIC ADAMS SPECTRAL SEQUENCE

This chart indicates the E_∞ -page of the motivic Adams spectral sequence. The chart is complete through the 90-stem, with partial results through the 95-stem.

For clarity, hidden extensions by 2, η , and ν are not shown on this chart.

See Section 4 for instructions on interpreting the chart. In addition:

- (1) Green vertical lines indicate hidden τ extensions.
- (2) Dashed lines of negative slope indicate unknown Adams differentials. Beyond the 90-stem, unknown differentials are not shown.

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